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Representative Virtual Material Collections about University Scientists: The Experience of the Uzhhorod National University Library

Objective. The research is aimed at studying practical experience of creation and application of the representations of virtual material collections about the scientists of the Uzhhorod National University, as one of the important popularization mechanisms of the university science. **Methods.** Using our own developments, we attempted to familiarize the library community with the specialized methodology of representation work of the scientific library of the Uzhhorod National University during quarantine restrictions and martial law in Ukraine. Using the comparative analysis, the efficiency of the representations of virtual material collections, created by the library as publicizing the development of university science and culture of the region and the interest of remote users in them has been proven. **Results.** The substantiation of the obtained results is based on the characteristics of the Uzhhorod National University library during remote work of the institution, aimed at increasing the interest of virtual users in the content of the library. The efficiency of using the method of representations of information products of libraries during the period of difficult physical access to the library funds of Ukraine has been confirmed. Analysis of the expansion of the library's information services and the practical recommendations regarding the active popularization of scientists and prominent figures of the Zakarpattia region are considered as one of the methods of reorienting the work of the library and its services in accordance with today's challenges. **Conclusions.** The important role of library support in the popularization of science and culture of the region, as an important factor of practical library assistance to society during the times of trials for Ukraine, has been confirmed.

Keywords: Scientific Library of the Uzhhorod National University; library innovations; representations of virtual materials; virtual exhibitions

Introduction

Despite the difficult events in the life of Ukraine, the period of the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russian-Ukrainian war, the library industry of Ukraine still experiences a rapid rise of innovative implementations. The tendency of introducing new methods in the work of libraries is caused by the urgent need for access to information. Education, employment relationship, a variety of online services through Internet communication channels have become a need of society. Information flows are produced each second, and their absorption is confirmed by the requirement of time. Today, Ukraine needs special informational support provided by the institutions and organizations. Among the variety of information resources, a significant part is produced by the libraries, which are entrusted with an important mission not only to preserve the cultural and scientific heritage of mankind, but also to promote their dissemination. A number of library scientists around the world study creation and presentation of library content in social networks, among which virtual exhibitions occupy an important place. The role, meaning and justification of the advantages of Facebook are studied on the example of the American public and scientific and university libraries (Aharony, 2012), the accents of advantages and disadvantages of Facebook in the work of university libraries (Margaix-Arnal, 2008); the issue of creating and distributing the virtual book exhibitions through virtual notification (Argasiński & Woynarowski, 2019). The methods of expanded user access to online services and content creation based on the functioning of the dominant social media of the scientific libraries in Ukraine, as a positive consequence of the remote work of librarians, a study of the Ukrainian library specialists (Petrushka, Kozhushana, & Manach, 2022); innovative transformation of the library work and drawing attention to the changes

in the educational and research ecosystems of the institutions during the period of uncertainty caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Kolesnykova, Gorbova, & Shcherbatiuk, 2022).

Purpose. As part of the study, it is aimed a) to analyze the presentation of virtual materials collections about the scientists and famous people of the Zakarpattia region, as a special digital content of the library of the Uzhhorod National University, distributed using Facebook, b) to determine the influence factors of the information product, as a new library service on remote user information requests.

Methods

Using the method of analysis of the communication interaction between the university library and the user audience on Facebook, it was attempted to present a specialized method of representing the virtual materials of the works of the scientific library of the Uzhhorod National University during the period of quarantine restrictions and the introduction of the martial law in Ukraine. Research methodology includes the methods of analysis, synthesis, comparison, grouping, generalization. Quantitative indicators of coverage (views), topics and user feedback were chosen as the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of representations of Facebook virtual collections. The important factors of adapting the work of the educational library to the changes in the information requests of remote users during the period of remote work of the library were identified, and the effective possibility of Facebook to expand the framework of the demand for the information needs of society was confirmed.

The analysis of the thematic dynamics of interest in the content proved that the virtual collections of materials effectively reflect the development of scientific achievements and cultural values of the region and play an important role in popularizing the achievements of the academic community in combination with the popularization of the library collections of the educational institution.

Results and Discussion

Scientific library of the Uzhhorod National University (hereinafter SL UzhNU) is one of the well-known educational libraries in Ukraine. Historical events of the Carpathian region development made a special imprint on the culture and education of the Zakarpattia region, including the first opening of a university and its library in the region. Today the UzhNU library has the most powerful collection of printed publications in Zakarpattia (more than 1,600,000 copies) and a collection of electronic academic texts (more than 55,000 files of full-text documents). 16,000 students study at the Uzhhorod National University, among which, despite the state of war in the country, more than 1,600 are foreign students, representatives of India, Nigeria, Jordan, Ghana, Palestine, Bangladesh, Western Europe and other countries. 1,256 teachers, including more than 177 doctors of science, professors, about 700 candidates of science, associate professors teach future specialists. The scientific library is an important structural unit of the university and plays a significant role in the quality of the educational process and the support of scientific research at the university.

The uniqueness of the westernmost educational library of Ukraine lies in the value of its collections, including more than 20,000 rare books, the analogues of which are few not only in Ukraine, but also in the whole world. Valuable collections of manuscripts and books always increase interest in the library, and the opportunity to use them opens the way for both domestic and foreign researchers. SL UzhNU has passed a long and thorny formation path, and today it is boldly mastering the latest library technologies, focusing on the European library standards. The

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library became one of the first libraries in Ukraine to implement an electronic library program in its work, which expanded its technological capabilities, and the use of new methods in serving modern users raised the image of the library.

The implementation of an innovative strategy in the development of the UzhNU library is primarily focused on advanced library technologies and practices. Despite the difficult political and economic conditions in the country, the library did not stop in its desire to meet the requirements of the time. The library structure is committed to the most productive capabilities of the team, therefore new departments have been identified in its structure, focused on using the best practices according to the requirements of the time, new plans have been developed, and new projects are being implemented. Unfortunately, raising the requirements to the level of the professional and informational skills of Ukrainian librarians does not correspond to their salary, on the contrary, during the period of the martial law in the country, it decreased somewhat, which causes staffing constraints when forming a group of leading library specialists and makes it difficult to replenish the team with IT specialists, whose support is extremely necessary for information development. And, even in spite of such difficulties, the library continues introducing innovations in its work: expanding the capabilities of the electronic catalog, applying a number of online services, updating the web-site, bibliometric and scientometric support of university scientists, holding a number of scientific conferences and many other applications that successfully raise the library status.

According to Tetyana Kolesnykova, a leading Ukrainian scientist in the field of librarianship, among the complex of innovative library services and creative solutions to support the creation, organization of access, dissemination, control and effective presentation of the achievements of the university scientists in the global information space, there is an important lever among the support services of scientific developments. It is the dissemination of the results of scientific research by scientists in the national and global scientific information space (Kolesnykova, 2023). With the aim of popularizing the science of the university, the SL UzhNU started the creation of representative virtual collections of materials of the university's scientists, aimed at spreading the achievements of scientists in the global Internet space. The concept of *representation* or *electronic presentation/exhibition* means the demonstration of virtual images of specially selected printed works and information about their authors in Internet using WEB technologies. The main purpose of the presentations is to present the materials about the scientist's life path and scientific development, an overview of his work, and familiarization with the author's books and the possibilities of their use to remote users. The advantage of representative virtual collections of materials is that they include a number of complementary features, such as: various images, videos, sound recordings, animation elements, digitization of original documents, etc. A significant advantage of material representations is their independence from the time of exposure, because the audience has access to the exhibitions long after they start their journey in the global electronic space. In comparison, their physical counterparts have limitations in time space, because they depend on the institution's work schedule.

The first presentations of representative virtual collections by the UzhNU library took place in 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic. They became a new challenge for the library as a separate project that was launched during the uncertainty associated with the period of the COVID-19 pandemic. The project was named "Virtual Book Exhibitions, Reviews, Presentations" (Scientific library of the Uzhhorod National University www.lib.uzhnu.edu.ua/node/61). It includes several thematic blocks, such as: New Arrivals, Literary Reviews, Thematic Exhibitions, Scientific Pride of the Uzhhorod National University, Dates and Events. After analyzing the concepts and typology of social networking sites, scientific library of the Uzhhorod National University reasonably chose Facebook, where the page Scientific library of the Uzhhorod National

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University www.facebook.com/libraryuzhnu was already created. This choice was based on the main criteria and evaluations of Facebook, which became the quantitative indicators of coverage, placement, comments and topics after a diachronic analysis of functioning of the dominant social media of the largest scientific libraries of Ukraine, among which were the libraries of the highest-rated higher educational institutions of the state.

The beginning of the implementation of the project “Virtual Book Exhibitions, Reviews, Presentations” was the middle of 2019. It included an initial period of discussion of issues related to the meaning of representations and their role in expanding the library powers. Simultaneously with the implementation of the mentioned project, the SL UzhNU initiated and successfully held a number of annual scientific and practical Internet conferences, which combined the discussion of the experience of virtual materials presentation by the library, as one of the levers of expanding the online services of the libraries. A conference held on June 18-25, 2019, entitled “Using Web Technology Instruments as a Basis for Expanding Library Online Services in the Creation of the Modern Library Image” was the beginning of the activities. One of the discussion areas were the issues “The Role of Social Information Communications in the Development of Libraries of Higher Educational Institutions” and “Online Services as Promising and Alternative Means of Library Services Development.” Among the many speakers at that meeting, it was presented the report by the Head of the Department of Cultural and Educational Work of SL UzhNU Khrystyna Nastych, named “Social Network Facebook in Work of Scientific Library” <https://dspace.uzhnu.edu.ua/jspui/handle/lib/24408>.

At the II Scientific and Practical Internet Conference “Modern Tasks and Priorities of the Library Activities: The Path of Innovation,” which took place on June 15-19, 2020 on the basis of the scientific library of the UzhNU, its chief bibliographer Olena Tsunyak presented the report “Development of Electronic Library and Information Technologies as a Component of the Image of Modern Libraries (On The Example of the Experience of the Scientific Library of the Uzhhorod National University)” <https://dspace.uzhnu.edu.ua/jspui/handle/lib/29293>.

The next, III Scientific and Practical Internet Conference organized by the UzhNU library within the framework of the mentioned project, took place on October 21, 2021 under the title “New Model of the Library’s Information Image: Changing the Traditional Perception of its Purpose and Functions” <https://dspace.uzhnu.edu.ua/jspui/handle/lib/38025>. Several reports of the conference participants are devoted to the experience issues of virtual materials representation in the UzhNU library. They are: “The Essence and the Value of Virtual Book Exhibitions as a New Form of Library Information Space” <https://dspace.uzhnu.edu.ua/jspui/handle/lib/29178>, which was presented by Iryna Lopit, the Head of the Main Subscription Department of the SL UzhNU; the report of the Head of the SL UzhNU, Mariia Medved, “Communicative Rehabilitation of the Library during Quarantine Limitations: The Experience of the Scientific Library of the Uzhhorod National University” <https://dspace.uzhnu.edu.ua/jspui/handle/lib/38033>; the report of the Head of the Local Literature Sector of the SL UzhNU Marija Chorny “Social Networks as a Lever for Popularization of Rare Local Publications from the Collections of the National Library of the Uzhhorod National University” <https://dspace.uzhnu.edu.ua/jspui/handle/lib/38070>.

The goal of the project “Virtual Book Exhibitions, Reviews, Presentations” was to master the skills of creating and representing virtual materials as a new online service from the library, which will not only tell about the life and scientific achievements of the UzhNU scientists, but also present their printed works from the collections of the university library. Representations gained particular popularity as a remote work opportunity for library employees, because this method facilitated the work of librarians to form content remotely at the time of physical distancing of the team during the coronavirus pandemic. This became a challenge to the possibilities of library professionalism, the ability to organize the work of the team and not to lose the user audience. At

this time, a significant part of sociocultural work moved into the virtual plane: video presentations, virtual exhibitions, virtual bookshelves, online flash mobs and promotions, etc.

Let us focus on one of the efficient work methods of the library team during the period of uncertainty – the creation of representative virtual material collections about the scientists of the Uzhhorod University, which combined various contents produced by the library. According to the librarian-scientists, one of the traditional forms of library activity that experiences an era of modernization and adaptation to a remote way of service is virtual (electronic) exhibitions, which are currently one of the most efficient forms of providing users with information (Turovska & Smoliar, 2015).

The present is filled with many challenges for libraries, and it is these challenges that push the libraries to master new work methods. Adaptation to the new requirements of world informatization promotes searching the ways to provide modern users with information, which make up the priority of requests. Such a new project for the SL UzhNU was the creation of its own electronic product, which is represented by a whole series of representations united by one name, but which differ in thematic blocks. The first of them was a representative virtual collection of materials, united by the series “Scientific Pride of the Uzhhorod University.” The main task of the newly created project was the combination of two main criteria: informing about the research achievements of the university scientists and accompanying presentation of the literary sources from the library collection, the authors/co-authors of which are university scientists.

The second block was the presentation of a representative virtual collection of the series “Prominent Figures of Zakarpattia.” It combined materials about prominent public, religious and cultural figures of Zakarpattia (writers, poets, artists, sculptors, journalists, scientists).

The third block was the series “The History of the UzhNU,” representative virtual materials of which included archival evidence of the formation of the largest university of the region – the Uzhgorod National University, from the time of its foundation to the present. In the series, the materials were grouped according to the different headings, among which a significant number consisted of thematic materials about the scientific library of the UzhNU.

Work on the creation of electronic information products was preceded by the training of library employees, which, by coincidence, fell on the pre-war period. It was a series of educational trainings aimed at acquiring the skills of creating informational electronic products, which became representative virtual collections of materials about the university scientists. The training included several stages: preparation and presentation of various images, ability to create and edit video, accompanying material with sound recording, digitization of original documents, animation, use of fonts and colors. The involvement of the team in the new project was perceived differently, some with ease and interest, others – with precaution. Over the years, the staff of the scientific library of the UzhNU has developed a special practical method of learning innovations – “colleagues teach colleagues,” so everyone joined the proposal to prepare one resource from the department. The situation determined the leaders in the creation of virtual representations, who were included in the main representative group of the creation of virtual exhibitions.

Soon, electronic exhibitions of materials created by the library gained considerable popularity among the users, because their demonstration in Internet, using WEB technologies, provided the opportunity to present materials to remote users and thus expand the framework of popularizing both the names of the scientists and the opportunity to advertise their works, which the SL UzhNU also keeps in its collections. Analytical indicators of attendance of various blocks are shown in Tables 1; 2; 3. The block “Scientific Pride of the Uzhhorod University” received the highest number of views. The number of views became the main argument for the interest of the remote audience in the representative materials about the scientists of the Uzhhorod University and interest in the library collections. The most important goal of the project, the librarians were

focused on, was successfully achieved, because it became the popularization of the scientific achievements of the Uzhhorod National University. The significance of virtual library exhibitions during a period of uncertainty is being explored by many library scientists, for example, Croatian librarians in the city of Zagreb. Studying the work of their library, they were mostly focused on virtual exhibitions and their demand during the period of quarantine restrictions caused by the COVID-19 (Semenski, Ille, & Cej, 2021).

The scientific library of the UzhNU has developed its own mechanism for selecting material for multimedia presentations based on the following criteria:

- selection of candidates of the scientists (authority of the scientists, their scientific merits and developments, scientometric characteristics, state assessment, etc. were taken into account);
- selection of sources from the library collection of the scientist's authorship (thematic search of books by authorship, by the field of scientific interests of the scientist: search in electronic, alphabetical and systematic catalogs of the library, in bibliographic indexes and based on the use of methodological recommendations);
- digitization of found sources;
- the scientist's consent to disclose personal archive materials and professional growth (family photos, diplomas and award documents, use of photocopies of archival and personnel documents);
- accompaniment of a virtual presentation with multimedia means (sound recording, video editing, animation, fonts and colors, etc.).

The first and most successful attempt of representation was a virtual exhibition of materials from the series "Scientific Pride of the Uzhhorod University" – "Professor Andrii Holovatskyi." It was dedicated to the 80th anniversary of Andriy Holovatskyi, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of Human Anatomy and Histology of the Medical Faculty of the Uzhhorod University. Interest in the presented material is confirmed by 6.5 thousand views (as of August 1, 2023), 1.6 thousand of which were collected during the first days of the demonstration.

Already in 2020, the library represented 12 personal exhibitions about the UzhNU scientists, which had 15,183 views, taking into account the fact that for the period 2020-2023, the number of views as of August 1, 2023 was about 30 thousand. Among the variety of representations, the greatest interest of virtual users was aroused by the virtual representations: about professor-linguist, the Head of the Department of Ukrainian Language of the UzhNU Natalia Venzhynovych (2.2 thousand views); the Head of the Department, Candidate of Biological Sciences, Associate Professor of the UzhNU Fedor Kurtyak (1.8 thousand views); Professor of the Department of Biochemistry and Pharmacology of the UzhNU Ivan Hryh (1.4 thousand views) and others. Regarding one of the representations of virtual materials, as a confirmation of the importance of popularizing the names of the university's scientists, the library received a comment from the network user Nataliia Roman "...It is incredibly interesting to walk along the scientific paths of the past. I am pleasantly surprised. I am sincerely grateful to those who give us this opportunity."

During the period 2020-2023, the scientific library will represent 36 virtual collections of materials about the UzhNU scientists.

The scientific library takes care of preserving the history of its native land. This is proved by the popularization of the names of prominent figures of Zakarpattia, most of whom are recognized by the state for their contribution to the cultural sphere of Ukraine. During the mentioned period, about 20 representations of outstanding public, religious figures, notable artists (writers, poets, sculptors, journalists, scientists) of the Zakarpattia region continue their mission of enlightenment in the Internet space. Like, for example, a virtual exhibition of materials for the

290th anniversary of the birth of the bishop of the Mukachevo Greek-Catholic Eparchy, the enlightener of Zakarpattia in the 18th century, Andrii Bachynskyi; to the 100th anniversary of the birth of the Ukrainian writer, prominent Zakarpattian, laureate of the Shevchenko Prize Ivan Chendei; about the patriarch of the Zakarpattia school of painting Volodymyr Mykyta and others. Representations of virtual collections of materials also tell about modern artists, such as: a talented Uzhhorod journalist and researcher of the history of Uzhhorod – Tetiana Literati, an artist – Odarka Dolhosh, awarded with the title of “Honored Worker of Culture of Ukraine,” a cymbalist – Leontii Lenart, and others. User interest in the presented materials is also quite high. For example, the virtual exhibition of materials about the famous Zakarpattia’s scientist-archaeologist Eduard Balahuri collected more than 2 thousand views; the exhibition about the original Uzhhorod artist Dmytro Chechko, which represented his paintings, was viewed more than 1.2 thousand times.

The series “The History of the Uzhhorod University” became no less popular for viewing by Internet users. Today, 17 representations walk through the Internet space. They tell the history of the creation and formation of the largest university in Zakarpattia. Among them documentary materials of the opening of faculties and departments are presented, the names of the first heads of the university or its structural units, their biographies, scientific growth are mentioned. The library supplemented the mentioned series with the materials about its formation: “A Book For All Time: Ancient Bibles in the Department of the Old Prints and Manuscripts of the Scientific Library of the Uzhhorod University,” “Virtual Excursion to the Largest Library of Zakarpattia: Based on the Monograph of the National Library of the Uzhhorod University: From the Origins to the Present,” “Treasures of the Scientific Library of the Uzhhorod University: A Unique Edition of the Rare Book Department “Галичанинъ,” “Cyrillic Handwritten Monuments From the Collection of the Scientific Library of the Uzhhorod University,” “Miniature Books From the Collection of the Scientific Library of the Uzhhorod University,” “Rare Editions of Encyclopedic Dictionaries From the Book Collections of the Department of Foreign Literature of the National Library of the Uzhhorod University” etc.

The virtual collection is complemented by the several virtual tours of the UzhNU library, including videos about the opening of the museums of the private book collections of Olena Rudlovchak – a scientist, former Transcarpathian, world-famous literary critic. Her library was transferred by her heirs to the scientific library of UzhNU from Slovakia and the Book Museum of Professor Vasyl Nimchuk. According to the will of a well-known linguist, it is also kept as a separate collection in the scientific library of UzhNU.

The representative virtual material collections created by the SL UzhNU continue their spread around the world, they have no borders and time barriers, they carry stories about talented people of Ukraine, their service to the state. Pages of encyclopedias and reference books, bibliographic indexes, articles on Wikipedia testify to the uniqueness of these people, their own works remain for posterity to be useful to new generations. Among all this diversity, virtual collections will remain a bright confirmation of recognition and gratitude to the talented compatriots.

Like all libraries in the world, the scientific library of the UzhNU takes care of the support and distribution of its electronic representations. Given that virtual representations can be distributed through different platforms, the university library uses different ways of popularization. They are:

- website of the scientific library of the Uzhhorod National University;
- social networks;
- university repository.

The website of the library (<http://www.lib.uzhnu.edu.ua/>) archives and provides free access to view representative materials using the heading “Information and Bibliographic Resources,”

which opens access to the sub-heading “Virtual Book Exhibitions, Reviews, Presentations.” In the section “Thematic Exhibitions”, along with the thematic material selections, representations of virtual exhibitions for the period 2019-2023 are included, the series “Prominent Figures of Zakarpattia” and “The History of the UzhNU.”

The series of representative virtual materials about the UzhNU scientists “Scientific Pride of the Uzhhorod National University” has a personal orientation and is distinguished by a special collection, with the date of the material presentation (year, month, time of day).

The library website helps to expand additional boundaries of representative virtual collections of materials in the heading “We are in Social Networks.” They present the pages of the scientific library of the UzhNU on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Telegram and YouTube. Facebook is still the most active.

The study is based on the analysis of the statistical dynamics of the creation and representation of virtual materials for the period 2019-2023.

Table 1

Series “Scientific Pride of the Uzhhorod University”:

Year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Exhibitions		12	8	11	5
Views		15183	11689	2038	434

Table 2

Series “Outstanding Figures of Zakarpattia”

Year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Exhibitions		4	3	6	5
Views		670	3236	1837	904

Table 3

Series “The History of the UzhNU”

Year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Exhibitions	1	6	4	3	2
Views	640	2230	941	707	355

Having monitored the representations, we can say that the period of uncertainty, which is considered the period of the COVID-19 pandemic (2020) and the beginning of Russia’s military attack on Ukraine (2022), was the most successful in creating representative virtual exhibitions of materials. The years 2020 and 2021 became the years of the most active audience interest.

In terms of interest in the representation, the highest rating (as of August 1, 2023) was given to the series “Scientific Pride of the Uzhgorod University,” which had 29,344 views on Facebook.

Conclusions

The creation of information resources by libraries has become a challenge of the conditions of information access, which are successfully implemented by Ukrainian libraries. The experience of the scientific library of the Uzhhorod National University in presenting representative virtual exhibitions of materials is based on the additional opportunity to popularize the names of the most authoritative scientists and figures of the Zakarpattia region, the history of the university’s development. Representations of the virtual exhibitions of materials have become an essential mechanism in popularizing and maintaining interest in the most authoritative names of Zakarpattia, as well as in their scientific work or educational activities. The formation of representations according to thematic characteristics of the collections reveals the importance of the development of science and culture of the region, popularizes the collections of the largest library in Zakarpattia, attracting an audience of thousands of virtual users to viewings, especially during quarantine and military events. Representations of virtual exhibitions of materials have become a successful project in the development of innovative technologies and the method of remote work of libraries.

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Репрезентативні віртуальні колекції матеріалів про вчених вишу: досвід бібліотеки Ужгородського національного університету

Мета. Дослідження спрямоване на вивчення практичного досвіду створення та застосування репрезентацій віртуальних колекцій матеріалів про вчених Ужгородського національного університету, як одного з вагомих механізмів популяризації науки університету. **Методика.** За допомогою власних напрацювань здійснена спроба ознайомити бібліотечну спільноту з профільною методикою репрезентаційної роботи наукової бібліотеки Ужгородського національного університету під час карантинних обмежень та воєнного стану в Україні. За допомогою порівняльного аналізу доведено ефективність репрезентацій віртуальних колекцій матеріалів, створених бібліотекою, як оприлюднення розвитку університетської науки та культури краю та зацікавленість ними віддалених користувачів. **Результати.** Обґрунтування отриманих результатів базується на характеристиці роботи бібліотеки Ужгородського національного університету під час дистанційної роботи установи, спрямованої на підвищення інтересу віртуальних користувачів до контенту книгозбірні. Підтверджено ефективність застосування методу репрезентацій інформаційних продуктів бібліотек за період складнощів фізичного доступу до фондів бібліотек України. Аналіз розширення інформаційних послуг бібліотеки та винесені практичні рекомендації щодо активної популяризації науковців та видатних постатей закарпатського краю розглянуто як один із методів переорієнтування роботи бібліотеки та її послуг відповідно викликам сьогодення. **Висновки.** Підтверджено важливу роль бібліотечної підтримки в популяризації науки та культури краю як важливого чинника практичної бібліотечної допомоги соціуму в період важких випробувань України.

Ключові слова: Наукова бібліотека Ужгородського національного університету; бібліотечні інновації; репрезентації віртуальних матеріалів; віртуальні виставки

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